

Our Heritage, Our Stories

Cinema Sgìre Project

Study into Community-Generated Digital Content

Prepared by the National Library of Scotland (project partner)

Year: 2024

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Background

Since the establishment of the Moving Image Archive in 1976 a close relationship has been cultivated over the years between the archive and various communities across Scotland. Part of this relationship includes local authority archives, museums and libraries who often discover moving image collections within their holdings but do not have the correct storage / skills for preservation or to make them accessible. Digitisation is a key component in all moving image collections in order to make them accessible. Repeated playback of fragile analogue formats places them at unnecessary risk of damage and in some cases destruction.

In February 2020, the National Library of Scotland Moving Image Archive was approached by Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean concerning video tapes they had in their collection. The videos were originally produced under the Cinema Sgìre community education project, which was based mainly in Uist and Barra, and ran from October 1977 until March 1981. As well as providing a mobile cinema service, the project included a video production element which involved local communities learning to record videos of everyday life in the islands. Set up by Comhairle nan Eilean, the original project was largely supported by the Scottish Film Council, the Highlands and Islands Development Board and the Gulbenkian Foundation.

The tapes were under the care of Museum nan Eilean but their obsolete, rare format, cost and complications of digitisation meant the content was impossible to access without specialist knowledge. Discussions between Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean and the Library were held to scope a project to digitise and catalogue the material. However, progress was initially limited due to various UK COVID lockdowns.

For the majority of collections that are held at the Moving Image Archive digitisation of the material can be completed inhouse. Provided permissions are obtained from copyright owners, this material is then subsequently made publicly available via an online catalogue. However, Cinema Sgìre required external funding due to the following factors:

- The Library did not have equipment to digitise over 100 video tapes of the specific obsolete EIAJ open reel format
- A Gaelic speaker was essential to catalogue the material
- No resources were available for public engagement activities

Project Management

A formal partnership between the Library and Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean was formed to develop the project. A donation agreement was signed which transferred the physical ownership of the tapes to the Library, however Museum and Tasglann nan Eilean would retain all Intellectual Property Rights. The roles and responsibilities for the project were divided as follows:

- The Library Development Team led on funding applications
- The Library led on procurement and award external contracts
- The Library managed external digitisation of the collection
- Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean managed public engagement activities

Meetings were held regularly, at least monthly, and on occasion every 2 weeks if required at specific stages. In May 2022 funding was secured from Bòrd na Gàidhlig and the Gaelic Language Promotion Trust. From June 2022 to January 2023 procurement exercises were conducted to contract:

- A facilities house to digitise the video tapes
- A company to catalogue the collection
- A company to devise and deliver public engagement and promotion of the collection within the island communities.

In January 2023 UistFilm, a production company based in the Outer Hebrides, were awarded the contract to catalogue, devise and deliver the public engagement activities. Due to the time constraints of the funding award, the project had to be completed by 31st August 2023. With digitisation of the original tapes complete by January 2023, the following timetable was agreed with UistFilm:

Work Plan	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August
Initial startup meeting	16th January							
Tape Review & Indexing								
Basic cataloguing								
Public engagement planning & promotion								
Public engagement Events								
Final cataloguing								
Completion & delivery								Report 12th August Return of materials 25 August

(Source: Project Final Report – UistFilm 2023)

Tape Quality & Content

As the image quality and content of the tapes were largely unknown prior to digitisation, the project was a gamble as to whether anything useable would remain of the recordings. The original project co-ordinator came forward with a typescript copy of the 1981 final report. From that report we learned that during the first year of filming the video crew had no access to editing facilities. Filming was patchy at times as the crew were learning how to use the technology. This, coupled with the added difficulties of recovering data from 45 year old recordings, made it difficult to plan the

public engagement ahead of cataloguing. From the cassette boxes we knew roughly the geographic areas that were supposed to be on the tapes, however as video could be recorded over, we could not rely on this information until the digitised tapes were actually viewed. This made the schedule for delivery very tight as our principal funding agreement was to complete the entire project over a year.

On viewing it was discovered that the signal loss on each tape varied. The tapes were also mostly a mixture of unedited raw footage of various community events. Uistfilm were required to edit sections together and undertake a limited amount of image and audio enhancement in order for the footage to be acceptable for public engagement. As the project was unable to secure additional funds for subtitling, only a 15 minute taster compilation was given bilingual captions.

Cataloguing

As previously mentioned part of the contract with UistFilm was to employ a Gaelic speaker to catalogue the films initially. This enabled a basic record to be created from which the public events programme could be planned and any sensitive issues within the content identified. The Library uses Filemaker Pro as the database system to hold all our records relating the Moving Image Archive. The database was designed inhouse and developed over the last 30 years as the needs of the archive changed. However the cataloguing rules are in accordance with the International Standard as guided by FIAF Cataloguing Standards.¹

The cataloguer was provided with a simple spreadsheet of the relevant column headings such as:

Accession Number ; Acquire ; Reason for Rejection ; Title ; Date ; Running Time ; Colour ; Sound ; Index Terms ; Synopsis ; Shotlist ; % of Gaelic content ; GDPR Issues ; Restrictions ; Cross over with other tapes

The column headings that matched the filemaker database for our records are typed in green in the above list. These columns were simply exported directly to filemaker for upload to our main catalogue to create a basic record. The Moving Image Archives uses an inhouse thesaurus of index terms for each title, again this was developed over a 30 year period by archive staff.

If a video was not selected for preservation the reason for rejection was recorded as being one of the following:

- Poor Technical Quality (unable to see or hear the content)
- Other examples already held (duplicate of another tape or similar content to other tapes but of less technical quality)
- Insufficient content of interest (majority of footage is too fragmented to make sense / long shots when camera accidentally left running)
- Title preserved elsewhere (poor quality off-air recording of a professional production for which better quality formats are preserved in other archives – BFI / BBC)

¹ [International Federation of Film Archives \(fiafnet.org\)](http://www.fiafnet.org)

The columns typed in red were project specific to assist us with clearly identifying tapes with potential issues such as duplication of content. A note of the percentage of Gaelic per title was included as this was a requirement of the funding application.

The formal Donation Agreement for the collection signed between The National Library of Scotland and Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean includes a Data Protection Statement. The questions asked are as follows:

1. Do any of Donated Items name or contain reference to (including pictures or moving images of) anyone that is still alive?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown, it is not practicable to know this	<input type="checkbox"/> No
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2. Do you have permission from the persons named or referenced in the Donated Items to donate the material with the Library for the purposes set out in this Agreement?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
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If you answered "Yes" to questions 1 and/or 2, please give details of the persons and evidence of their permission, if obtained, on a separate sheet attached to this Agreement.

3. Do any of the Donated Items include any of the following personal data of persons alive? (tick all that apply)

3.1	Name and contact details (address, email address, and/or telephone numbers)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.2	Age or date of birth	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.3	Racial or ethnic origin	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.4	Political opinions	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.5	Religious or philosophical beliefs	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.6	Trade Union membership	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.7	Physical or mental health	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.8	Sex life or sexual orientation	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.9	Criminal convictions and offences or alleged offences	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.10	Genetic or biometric data	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you said "Yes" to any part of question 3, please give details of the nature and location of this information within the Donated Items on a separate sheet attached to this Agreement.

Invariably, this Statement is not completed with any details because until the collection is reviewed, GDPR issues are unknown and within the material. Also permissions from those appearing in moving images are rare as it is simply not practical to identify each person and research their contact details. A Gala Day or community event is widely attended and staff resources are not available to perform that level of detailed research. It is also not practical to expect a donor to undertake that task. With regard to family films, families can lose contact for a number of reasons so again permissions are not also possible.

In the case of Cinema Sgìre, GDPR issues and any potential restrictions due to content were highlighted by the cataloguer. The Library and Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean staff would discuss the issues raised in accordance with guidance provided by The National Archives.² Processing of personal data for archival purposes has long been included under UK Data Protection Legislation. As the National Library of Scotland and Museum & Tasglann nan Eilean are both public bodies, material selected for preservation would be considered to be of public interest with regard to the processing of data. Although the UK Data Protection Act does not define exactly 'archiving in the public interest', the following description is given:

- Public authorities or public or private bodies that hold records of public interest should be services which, pursuant to Union or Member State law, have a legal obligation to acquire, preserve, appraise, arrange, describe, communicate, promote, disseminate and provide access to records of enduring value for general public interest.³

Any material highlighted by the cataloguer would be reviewed if made accessible would cause:

- substantial damage would be financial loss or physical harm;
- substantial distress would be a level of upset, or emotional or mental pain, that goes beyond annoyance or irritation, strong dislike, or a feeling that the processing is morally abhorrent⁴

Again the UK Data Protection Act 2018 does not define 'substantial damage'.

As the Western Isles is such a close knit community the input from local staff with their detailed knowledge and experience was invaluable to this process. The range of issues discovered included clearly readable or audible special category data concerning members of the community. Other restrictions on accessibility that were considered concerned the level of bad language that may make the title inappropriate for open access. In one case the signal loss was so poor on a film that a warning was added for those with photosensitive epilepsy. Recommendations on varying levels of access were suggested that would allow certain tapes to be made available on request only and not online.

The catalogued videos were then made available via the Library's online catalogue a few weeks after the launch of the public engagement programme. Only a few videos have not been uploaded due to GDPR concerns arising from the content. There were also tapes that were not selected for preservation due to poor image / audio quality or they were inferior duplicates of other recordings. The catalogue can be accessed via this link: <https://movingimage.nls.uk/search?personality=10083>

Public Engagement

The public engagement activities were a mixture of in-person and online events. The areas selected were determined by the usable content on the tapes. This was to enable the videos made by specific communities to be shown back in those

² [Archives and GDPR: frequently asked questions - Archives sector \(nationalarchives.gov.uk\)](#)

³ [Guide to archiving personal data \(nationalarchives.gov.uk\)](#) P.21

⁴ [Guide to archiving personal data \(nationalarchives.gov.uk\)](#) P16

locations. The audience saw onscreen their own friends, relatives and local events from the late 1970's. The events were presented bilingually, however there was one online event that was presented solely in Gaelic.

The programme of events also considered audiences of different generations so that schools were accommodated as well as care home visits and general inter-generational community screenings:

Area	Number of events	Additional information
Barra & Vatersay	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Including 1 Care Home and 1 Day Care Centre
South Uist	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Including visits to 2 Primary School groups. 1 event included a befriending/dementia group invited to attend an afternoon session.
Benbecula	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 event was a wool-related compilation specifically requested for screening at the inaugural Uist Wool Festival.
North Uist	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 of these events was a compilation shown at the Hebrides International Film Festival in Carinish, repeated over several evenings. 1 Care Home event. 1 event is the ongoing Cinema Sgìre exhibition currently in Gallery 2 at Taigh Chearsabhaigh, open 6 days a week for 4 weeks.
Harris & Scalpay	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Community Event in Harris 1 Community Event in Scalpay
Lewis	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 of these events was a compilation shown at An Lanntair prior to scheduled cinema films, repeated over a fortnight, to large audience numbers. 2 events were at Care Homes.
Online screenings	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 online event was held in Gaelic The 2nd online event was held bilingually, with an online audience also gathered in Taigh Chearsabhaigh.
Other(Mòd Ionadail Dhùn Eideann)	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The National Library of Scotland's Learning & Outreach Officer screened a compilation of footage at the NLS's stand at the Edinburgh Local Mòd.
Total	28	

(Source: Project Final Report – UistFilm 2023)

The screening events themselves had a core programme that was generic to showcase the entire collection and the location specific extracts were added for each audience. The venues chosen for public screenings were community owned and when possible involved local community groups. The local groups helped to further promote the project amongst their members and encouraged attendance.

Tea and biscuits were served after each screening to encourage the audience to discuss what they had seen and to share their memories. In some cases this was the

first opportunity many smaller communities had met together since COVID restrictions were lifted.

There were also clips added to a dedicated Facebook page to promote the project and publicise the collection to a wider audience. The Facebook posts were tagged into the social media networks of many supporting organisations so they reached a wide global audience. UistFilm also used Vimeo as a method to send specific links to full versions of the videos to selected individuals to gather further information to enhance the accuracy of the cataloguing descriptions. Audiences attending the screenings were also encouraged to complete a feedback form which provided the opportunity to gather more detailed information. This form of targeted crowd sourced cataloguing was something that the Library had not engaged in before and had mixed levels of success.

The taster 15 minute screener was shown at the International Hebridean Film Festival and has since been used at Gaelic Edinburgh Week to promote the collection post-project. Local and National press, radio and television covered the events throughout the duration of the project and were extremely supportive and positive.

Audience Feedback

The audience feedback was delivered via a written form or informally during the discussions after the screenings. Many of the comments received demonstrated the audience appreciation and importance of archival materials shared within the communities that made them. In the final project report UistFilm reflected on discussions concerning Gaelic language:

“Many commented on the Gaelic spoken in the films, the wealth of vocabulary used, the fluency of the children, their confidence in the language, and how Gaelic was the language of the community. The language used in the films themselves is not exclusively Gaelic, not even close, but the subject matter lends itself to be used in Gaelic contexts, and in Gaelic Arts and heritage activities. The archive is now available to promote Gaelic in digital learning and usage, as a resource for further study of Gaelic language, culture, and community development.”

Eilidh Johnson, UistFilm reported via email concerning feedback she personally received:

“I bumped into one of the fishermen from the films today and he said how pleased he was to see the recordings from all those years ago, memories of seasick camera crews, a school pupil nearly falling overboard, the anecdotes from Cinema Sgìre go on and on! It has been great to meet people from all over the islands and hear all their connections and the background stories to the films.”

One of the videos is an example of cooperation between archival institutions when it was shared with National Library of Wales Screen and Sound Archive. The tape concerns the protests for Welsh language broadcasting. It is believed to have been presented as part of a conference in Stornoway. Iola Baines, Moving Image Curator commented:

“We at the National Library of Wales Screen and Sound Archive were thrilled to discover that a videotape with footage of such a historic Welsh event had come to light during the Cinema Sgìre project. We had no idea what to expect when the viewing file arrived, but soon realised that it contained unique footage of a key event in the campaign for Welsh language television, showing scenes and crowds outside the Carmarthen courthouse where the case of two key activists was being heard in July 1978. Many prominent people in the language movement are featured, with more yet to be identified...”

It is hoped that the availability of this collection will inspire other projects and encourage new collaborations for those researching Gaelic language and culture. The digital files are accessible via the Library’s online catalogue which facilitates research and enjoyment of these recordings beyond the geographic boundaries of the Outer Hebrides. The public engagement programme re-envigored connections within the island communities themselves and this has been one of the most gratifying aspects of the project. The public screenings provided the opportunity for smaller communities to get together in person. This was particularly noted as a very welcome development after COVID lockdowns. Local community groups and community owned venues were very supportive of the public engagement programme and were enthusiastic to support the project. Online discussions via various social media groups within the islands demonstrated the positive public response to the material.

The legacy of the project could include future collaboration with Tobar an Dualchais in connection with joint holdings of shared contributors and themes. The Library has already shown an edited showreel at Gaelic Week in Edinburgh to promote and engage Gaelic communities living outside of the Outer Hebrides. Through the Library’s Gaelic Residency, the collection is available to be linked to other Gaelic collections.

Conclusion

This project would not have been possible without external funding to digitise the original material and contract a local company with the necessary moving image skills to disseminate the collection within the islands.

The Moving Image Archive works with many different community groups from all over Scotland, however without additional resources, projects to process and promote them are unfortunately few and far between. Moving Image Collections are labour intensive and require a variety of skills before they become accessible to the public. Projects such as Cinema Sgìre demonstrate what is achievable when that extra resource is secured. However, there are aspects of this project that additional funding would have increased the accessibility even further. Primarily this would have been with the addition of bilingual subtitles for every film, ideally with BSL (British Sign Language) interpretation. This would have assisted non-Gaelic speakers but also any deaf or hard of hearing viewers. Similarly audio descriptions could be added to assist those with visual impairment. The footage itself would also

have benefited from visual and audio digital restoration and enhancement to improve the viewing experience as the signal quality was poor in places.

The Cinema Sgìre Project was only the initial steps in releasing the potential of this collection. The funding was concentrated on the initial digitisation, cataloguing and public engagement within the Outer Hebrides. Now that the material is digitised, catalogued and available to view online, the potential for this collection to reach more people and inspire future projects will only continue. The material was well used and publicised within the islands and will continue to be discussed within the local communities and elsewhere. The strength of this collection was that it was filmed by the community about the community. This contrasts with the larger body of archival material that is created by visitors to the islands and their observations on the local communities. Much of the feedback received focused on the richness of the Gaelic language spoken in the videos and the art of storytelling which has declined over the decades. As the recordings included people and places well known to the local communities it has stimulated much reflection on the history of the islands and how important that was for future generations. As the project is still relatively new it is too early to predict the full benefits that digitisation of the collection will bring. However, many potential ideas were suggested and discussed as a result of the public engagement programme and other opportunities may arise as time goes on.